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Recruitment strategies for international projects- A case study on Chinese construction companies in Bangladesh

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Abstract: Human resource is an important advantage for the development business since this segment utilizes more workforces in its business exercises contrasted with different segments. Human asset rehearses are normally worried to pick up an incentive through improved aptitudes, experience, self-sufficiency, commitment, efficiency, and lost awareness. Enlisting the certified representatives is a standout amongst the most imperative and most basic pieces of human asset the board.

The main focus of this research is to find out the process and way of recruiting employees for construction projects in Bangladesh done by Chinese companies. This study also focuses on the strategy of recruiting competent members for the company and organization. This study will equally help to understand about the effective way of recruiting and selecting employees and will also give an idea about the improvements needed during the process of recruitment.

Both qualitative and quantitative data is used for research. The research method comprised interviews with experts, a questionnaire based on recruitment, and selection strategies were sent to a sample of 100 practitioners to elect the most important factors. SPSS V23.0 is used for data analysis.

Findings reveal that most of the companies have a structured way to recruit their employees. If any vacancies occur, the campiness looks for the qualified people within the company. If not found, they go for different agencies. If not found again, they go for traditional advertisement or employer referrals. Respondents expressed that the method for enrolling and determination ought to be entirely followed so as to guarantee that the correct materials are accommodated the organization.

Keywords: Recruitment Strategies, Construction Projects in Bangladesh, Chinese companies, Recruitment for international projects.

Chapter One

Introduction

1.1 Background of the Study

Bangladesh-China, two time-tested and all-weather friends who have a relationship that dates back to centuries. Primeval China & Indian subcontinent was connected by ancient Silk Road by three routes, among them, the southern silk route was the bridge between the eastern parts of Bengal which is today's Bangladesh. The moving worldwide focus of financial gravity towards the east has made space to re-establish their historic network. China even made it stronger by re-introducing the B&R initiative and let the world adopt the 'Look East Policy'. Bangladesh is more likely a sandwich between India and China for its geopolitical situation. (Islam, 2012) And recent investments in Bangladeshi will surely give China an edge over India. China has always seen itself as a very important destination for outward FDI projects in Bangladesh. During July-September, 2018, 36.29% of total FDI came from Chinese investments, mostly investing in Power, Construction, Textile, NBFi and Railway projects. (Foreign Investment & External Debt (FIED) Cell, 2018)

In advanced nations the generally used the practices of project management for its public and private zones while the least established countries are still in the early stage in such manner. Human resource is a key resource for a country, a key resource for an organization, a key resource for an association Bangladesh got a lot of HR and organizations are procuring those benefits for their association. What's more, for the efficiency improvement project management is coming into the limelight. Numerous organizations he undertaking the board in practically every one of the tasks they are taking to develop their business. Project management has process influenced various organizations to be progressively compelling and to achieve

economic advancement arrange. In spite of the fact that the usage of project the board tools methods still before all else stage open area associations are likewise partaking in the act of task the project management constantly. Lately, project management preparation turned into a key factor to accomplish objective through activities both in private and open area companies. Likewise, performance estimate and supportable advancement is the extra characteristic of project management (Rahman & Bach, 2018).

Having the right team for the project is one of the key parts for project success. Without the correct set of teams set up even the potential projects with great plans and strategies has a big chance of failing. All the team members should have a similar vision and commitment for the overall success of the projects. Project managers can confront genuine inconvenience if insufficiency is present within the project team. It is vital to appoint the right individuals to each aspect and ensure that they are functioning well together (PALMER, 2018).

Project delay, which costs both extra time and money, is a common phenomenon in the developing countries. Delay caused by team members is one of the main reasons in project delay. Therefore, project success largely depends on project team members. (Tripathi, 2015) The achievement of a business or an association is legitimately connected to the execution of the individuals who work for that business. Underachievement can be a consequence of work environment disappointments. Since enlisting the wrong individuals or neglecting to envision changes in contracting needs can be expensive, it is critical that cognizant endeavors be put into human resource planning. (Ng & Sears, 2017).

The process of recruitment and selection are the way toward pulling in people on an appropriate idea, in adequate numbers, and with fitting abilities. Accordingly, recruitment is the route toward recognizing and attracting potential hopefuls from inside and outside of an organization to begin evaluating them for future business. Selection at that point starts when the correct measure of candidates is recognized. Selection is in this manner the procedure through which companies settle

on choices about who will or will not be permitted to join the company (Marchington, Kynighou, Wilkinson, & Donnelly, 2016). The selection procedure fluctuates from project to project, company to company, employment to the occupation, and nation to nation. A portion of the procedures consolidates screening applications and continues, testing and investigating work tests, meeting, checking references. Organizations use these methods to improve the likelihood of employing people who have the correct aptitudes and capacities to be effective in their professions (Renwick, Redman, & Maguire, 2012).

There has been a lot of research looking at what aptitudes and characteristics managers' esteem most in hire candidates. Abilities, work involvement, and communication or relational abilities are the most habitually identified characteristics. Work understanding and capabilities are proportions of ability in connection to a candidate's specialized aptitudes, while the idea of relational abilities gives off an impression of being a conventional term consolidating a wide range of explicit abilities. For sure, communication in the work environment includes group skills; administration abilities; a capacity to consult with or convince others; critical thinking abilities; hierarchical abilities; and introduction talents. Other communication abilities incorporate social adjustment, social ability and language capability. A candidate's prosperity with job looking for is identified with their capacity to depict their encounters, abilities and learning through a scope of media.

Along these lines, viable communication is a fundamental competency required by all activity candidates. To deal with a different workforce adequately, a company must contract and advance the most competent candidate for a work, while being aware of the need to manufacture a workforce that is illustrative of the more noteworthy business network. This might be accomplished by utilizing increasingly suitable and comprehensive enlistment and determination systems. In spite of an ongoing increment in distributed writing talking about enrollment and determination rehearses, there has been little change in the sorts of strategies used to enlist and choose workers. These days an ever-increasing number of organizations comprehend the significance of human talent and its impact on the effective activities of a task. It's anything but a

mystery that different enterprises give a ton of consideration to the enrolling procedure and prosperity of their representatives, as individuals are the primary resource in the project management. Even though a company has a good strategy and sustainable funds, it will not reach success without loyal and well-trained human resources.

As an organization needs to succeed and endure, or contend adequately in the worldwide economy in this period of globalization, managers must be in the situation to propound and rehearse enrollment and determination of workers in the most ideal manner. The accomplishment of an undertaking is legitimately connected to the execution of the individuals who work in it. Underachievement can be an aftereffect of working environment disappointments. Each venture has its very own prerequisites in obtaining employees. It is fundamental that organization select individuals with the quality basic for proceeded with accomplishment in this aggressive worldwide town and choose them for the correct venture. The main methods for making this progress is through appropriate selection and recruitment practices. (Sadiq, Fareed, Ikhlaq, & Mujtaba, 2013)

The importance of recruitment and selection can assume urgently imperative job in molding a company's feasibility and performance, if work companies can get laborers who as of now have applicable information, abilities and aptitudes and can make a precise expectation with respect to their future abilities. Recruitment and selection additionally have a vital task to carry out in guaranteeing specialist performance and positive authoritative results. It is regularly asserted that selection of workers happens not simply to supplant withdrawing representatives or then again add to a workforce yet rather hopes to set up experts who can perform at an unusual dimension and show responsibility (Louw & J., 2013).

By utilizing the accurate selection strategies one can guarantee that the applicant does not just has the correct abilities for the activity, yet additionally has the right identity to fit into the current hierarchical culture. When that "right" individual has been utilized, the organization needs to guarantee that the exact persuaders are set up. In any case recruitment and selection are portrayed

by potential challenges and it is important to stay up to date with improvements in research in the field of undertaking. Recruitment and selection process are imperatively critical to any association burning of drawing in and naming qualified work force. Getting the right individuals in the opportune spot at the time doing the accurate activity is a basic component of recruitment and selection process in associations. All together for the procedure to meet wanted objectives, it must be legitimate and quantifiable, with least antagonistic effect.

Basically, recruitment and selection staff is costly both as far as time and cash and it is subsequently critical that the way is completed easily and proficiently and results in the arrangement of an individual who fits the activity. Companies exist not in view of their desire to be noble but rather to likewise make benefit. In spite of the fact that their underlying concern might be that of picture building and winning the generosity of people in general, however a definitive objective is the accomplishment of the substantial goals. This implies there is the need to design deliberately to provide food for the short, medium-and long-haul development of the company. The organization reliably recruits new students from various nations and with different foundations to create new thoughts and grow their business to new markets. Along these lines, the human resource is vital in the organization, as the workforce changes quickly and development organizations needs to nonstop improvement in the HR practice.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

As the field of project management is getting maturing in theory and practically globalization calls for an increased interaction between people of different countries and cultures, it has witnessed a “projectification” of the world led by a growing number of specialists organizing their work in projects rather than on on-going functional basis. With this increasing number of projects abroad, the Chinese firms need to make sure that they keep their reputation while working abroad. In addition, to do the projects abroad, an international team with an international standard as the project success depends a lot on the project team members. Therefore, the most troublesome is to identify skilled labors for a changing environment, as all the international projects are mostly different in nature. It is very tough for the managerial staffs to recruit the suitable person in this case and it is very important for the managerial staffs to select the best personnel from numerous

job applications. (Hsu, 2016) Almost one third of the business failure occurs for inability to recruit high talent and poor hiring decisions. Especially it is more difficult in the emerging markets, making the most use of the resources is difficult for the organizations as well. (Dewhurst, Harris, & Heywood, 2012) Recruitment strategies in different countries might not go with the company culture. However, the earlier the company finds out the effective way of talent recruitment, the better for the company.

1.3 Significance of the study

1.3.1 Practical Significance

Through this study, it is possible to know which type of recruitment system is good for Chinese firms for their international projects in Bangladesh. We would be able to know where the companies lack while recruiting and finding the best way to recruit workers for the international projects. Even it will be possible for the job seekers to get some ideas that how the companies are recruiting for their international projects. Furthermore, findings may influence positive social change by providing a greater understanding of employee recruitment efforts, thus reducing time hazard during the project and improving the project health.

1.3.2 Theoretical Significance

The findings, conclusions, and recommendations stemming from my study may be valuable to senior management, human resource leaders, and lead engineers for creating and deploying strategic and derivative operational plans to address attrition and skilled project worker shortages. Through improved recruiting strategies, decision-makers may develop and implement improved talent acquisition processes and thereby reduce unemployment.

1.3.3 Social Significance

Findings from this research may contribute to positive social change by identifying new ideas and innovative strategies to respond to recruitment challenges. These ideas may support the reduction of the unemployment rate for skilled labor. The findings can provide greater opportunities and access to employment that provide livable wage earnings.

1.4 Research Objective

The purpose of this study is to explore the recruitments strategies the recruiters should follow during their recruitment for international projects. The recruitment process for international projects will be investigated to manage the recruitments challenges, which have been faced by Chinese companies in Bangladesh.

1.5 Research Question

1. Which medium should Chinese companies use to recruit employees for their projects in Bangladesh?
2. How should Chinese companies select their employees for their international projects in Bangladesh?

1.6 Scope of the Study

The study will be done within Chinese companies having different projects in Bangladesh, in which various strategies for recruitment system will be discussed which includes traditional advertising; head hunting, e recruiting and network-based recruiting & the specific ways of recruiting project team members will be discussed in a brief.

1.7 Methodology

We can gain the understanding of underlying opinions, motivations and reasons by qualitative research and quantitative research provide us information and results through instrument. The present study of nature is exploratory research. Generally, the data collection method for qualitative research is unstructured or semi-structured. Individual interviews, focus group, and observations are some common methods that are used to collect data. Typically, the sample size is small. While quantitative research quantifies the problem by generating data that is transformable to statistics. In Quantitative research, data collection is much more structured than qualitative research. Some of the common methods are different types of surveys including paper surveys, online surveys, mobile surveys, online polls and so on. This thesis conducted as qualitative and quantitative research and the methodological orientation more specifically is a factist perspective. The information, which is retrieved from the questionnaire as well as interviewees more or less, presents the reality. Therefore, the interest is to collect the data through questionnaire and

interviews. I chose a quantitative and qualitative study design that explored certain challenges and influences of the participants. Primary data has been used to perform the research. To collect the primary data, the employees from the construction sector of different companies have been selected for data collection through questionnaires and semi-structured interviewed had done.

1.8 Organization of the Study

The study consists of five main steps that description and figure 1.1 below:

First Step: Problem Description

The first step consists of the background to the study, statement of the problem, Scope of the study, Objective of the study and significance of the study and lastly the organization of the study

Second Step: Literature Review

About fifty references reviewed from various papers including books, articles, and official reports. These existing literature studied instantly to investigate recruitment and selection strategies used to select appropriate strategies for an international project.

Third Step: Research Methodology

The third step is the research methodology which adapted to conduct the research was stated. This step deals with issues such as the research design, instrument and data collection tools, and data analysis.

Fourth Step: Data Analysis

The fourth step deals with data presentation, discussion, and analysis.

Fifth Step: Conclusion and Recommendations

The fifth step indicates the findings of the study, conclusion, and recommendations.

Figure 1.1: The Presentation of the Research Framework

Chapter Two

Literature Review

This part manages the evaluation of literature works, which identify with the subject the recruitment and selection strategies for developing international projects activities in Bangladesh. A few writings would be chosen and applicable territories would be checked on and assessed. This part gives data about part of past works which identify with this examination. Recruitment and selection strategies are indispensable elements of HR for a business organization. These are terms that refer to the way toward drawing in and picking possibility for business. The nature of the human resource the firm has intensely relies upon the adequacy of these two capacities. Enrolling and choosing the wrong hopefuls who are not competent accompanied a vast negative cost which organizations cannot manage. Subsequently, the general point of recruitment and selection methodologies for recruiting employees inside the company is to get the number and nature of representatives that are required to fulfill the vital targets of the company at negligible expense.

2.1. Definition of Key Concepts

2.1.1. Project

As indicated by Zimmermann, J. et al. (2010), a venture an exertion started to accomplish explicit objectives, which requires to be cultivated inside a particular start and end time and through a confined at risk of assets.

Melton, T (2008), weights that a project is interpreted to connote a sovereign endeavor with an extraordinary assurance and circumstances to be cultivated by mimicked associations or viable frameworks. It is proficiently working to synchronize and adapt people to work concerning a customary focus to complete an obligation.

Cleland (2014) clarifies a project as the method for bearing special values to be consumed so as to fulfill both interests supply an arranging is the thing that association actualize with its technique that will accomplish association an objective to improve development execution and total task at a given timeframe to indicate opening date of an undertaking on its destination period. From which

a project get to be finished a task is attempted with a key of accomplishing the time, cost, specialized done effectively the association system are given out through undertaking this where that is there is a similarities between project managerial & strategic evidence that depicts four thought that are constantly engaged with a project cost, time, method help and ability and undertaking that outcome on appropriate great plan to execute the association technique.

A project is embraced with the point of accomplishing the time, cost & technical performance goals. The procedures are actualized through tasks, this is the place the connection between project management & strategic management evident (Wagner 2015). The four key contemplations that are constantly engaged with a venture are time, cost, technical performance capability, & the results fit into the structure and execution of authoritative systems.

2.1.2 International Projects

The literature review was conducted based on the main steps of scoping the review, determining keywords and search strings, identifying relevant search databases, applying the search to uncover relevant literature, and extracting findings relevant from the literature to our research. In scoping the review, we decided to limit the focus to success factors; on one hand in traditional projects and on the other hand in international projects (Yasin, Zimmerer, and Wafa 2015). The rationale for this scope was that the paper's main aim is to contrast success factors in traditional and global projects as well as extending the insight into how a case company can improve the success of its international projects. The search criteria were defined as 'success factors', 'project' and 'international project'.

Some seemingly established facts about projects; project work is a common way of organizing business (Pinto, J.K. and Slevin, D.P. 2016), is of high strategic importance for the project-oriented company and has evolved to become the principal means for dealing with change in modern organizations (Cleland and Ireland, 2014). However, increasingly, companies run international projects across national borders. Such projects differ from traditional projects in many ways: In traditional projects, a large majority of the team members are working for the same organization

and in a single location. This contrasts with international projects, which involve team members from different cultures, working in many locations, for many different organizations, across country borders. As a result, the international project manager must deal with cross-cultural and language differences as well as different time zones (Binder, 2015). Furthermore, international projects are typically operated in unfamiliar environments, e.g., in politically unstable countries and with unfamiliar suppliers involved. Since global projects involve collaboration between participants from multiple countries, they face unique challenges that are not faced in intra-national projects; challenges related to differences in work practices, legal regulations and cultural value (Mahalingam and Levitt, 2014). Interactions among individuals, organizations and agencies from diverse national backgrounds and cultural contexts, even on technologically routine international projects, often lead to misunderstandings, increased transaction costs, friction between project participants, and coordination and communication difficulties (Ng, Dyne, and Ang 2009). These in turn also contribute to additional costs and time overruns that are often a significant portion of original project estimates (Orr, 2013). Such costs and risks are nontrivial and are unique to international projects.

2.1.3 Project Management Practice in Bangladesh

In developed countries, though the project management practice is implemented both in public and private sector, but the least developed countries are still in the early phase in this regard. Bangladesh is independent in the year 1971. Since the economic growth required rapid development and various social issues need to be solved immediately. Public sector was playing the controlling role in the economic development of Bangladesh (Fisher, E. 2011). As political situation changes in the mid-seventies private sector got the favor to play in the development of the economy.

As per the definition private sector organization is easier to change its nature rather than public sector organization. Project management is now days implemented in private sectors more than the public sector organizations. There are around 52 MNCs and 200 local companies in Bangladesh already started implementation of project management into their organizations (Bryde, D. 2008). Some well-known private companies namely: Grameenphone Ltd., Robi Axiata Ltd., Banglalink,

Airtel, Symphony etc. already implemented PMO in their organizations. These are only a few names among the numbers. In public sector, the project management practices in infant stage (Muenjohn 2009). Like other developing countries, Bangladesh also facing lots of social, economic, administrative and political constraints. It is in south Asian region of the world. The economic condition of Bangladesh was vulnerable.

From the last decade some improvement is started. Now the GDP of Bangladesh is \$325.1 billion and \$2080 is per capita. Comparing other countries, its economic condition is growing better. Bangladesh is very much well known for its huge population and density of population. Bangladesh has plenty of human resources; companies are hiring that asset for their organization. In addition, for the productivity improvement project management is coming into the lime light (Kerzner, H. 2013). Many companies already started to practice the project management in almost all the projects they are taking to grow their business. Project Management has process made a number of companies to be more effective and to reach sustainable development stage (Wells, 2012).

2.1.4 Project Management in Construction

In general, construction projects in developing countries fail to reach target regarding predefined budget and time with desired quality due to failure of identifying and estimating unanticipated risk as well as recruiting HR for managing international projects. According to (Leung et al., 1998; Kerzner's (2014), "an effective recruitment approach can provide a framework for project managers to identify and assess potential in candidate's and take response actions in order to achieve the desired objectives of a given project". He further applied knowledge-based technique, developed a model for discovering probable recruitment process of a project by using previous experience, and proved its feasibility in real field. Robert (2001) discovered that the effectiveness of recruitment depends on the process of person identification and assessment as well as proposed the most effective sequences of human management system as "knowledge acquisition, selection of the core design team, presentation of the process, identification, encoding and verification".

As per (Jung and Avolio 2011; Chris C. 1997) has provided a summary of recruitment and selection process which was the synthesized of methods and concluded that project management is the right of the project itself depending on objectives, assigned task and system of project delivers. Usually sometime project is viewing as negative aspect and meaning financial loss, occurrence of hazard, adverse effect etc. Although, procedures available for project experts are mostly to pay attention in negative side, David (2002) studied to widen the possibility of project management process using project opportunity administration. S C Ward (1999) studied the inadequacies of ranking project factors based on probability and impact method. He concluded that management would be most effective if both size and probability of occurring impacts are distinguished with response timely. Since project factors are varied in project-to-project, associated risk also varied. However, project manager frequently worked with common and even irrelevant issued for risk minimization, which are proved ineffective and intentionally avoid most effective causes of risk for difficulties. For effective risk management, it is necessary to discover most important relevant as well as irrelevant information to give emphasize and exclude respectively (Elmar & Mark, 2010).

Ofer & Mark (2011) have done an extensive study for evaluating the efficiency of current practice of management to minimize the project management. That study collected data from multinational industries from different countries and regions. The research found that the level of project and its intensity varies with respect to above contexts and proper planning of project management are adequate to diminish risk for successful project completion. Martin (2007) has been studied post mortem analysis for project assessment, which is commonly used in software-based management system. This analysis found most efficient for providing detailed information to enhancement capacity of the project future and evaluated the value of participating all categories project personnel to know how best management techniques.

Terry & Martin (2004) conducted a research survey within senior executive of Queensland construction industry regarding the commonly used techniques of international project handling. Research identified higher practice of project management in planning and implementation stage

of project than starting and ending phases; priority given to identify and assess of risks prior to action taken, qualitative and response method were commonly used practice respectively. Nabil & Saied (2001) also have done a questionnaire through largest construction industries in Kuwait from the view of contractors to evaluate the action taken for time and cost related project management. Besides, in Kuwait, research found that contractors were eager to receive legal and agreement related project and application of proper project management practice was limited. However, a new concept in identifying and assessing potential project concurrently by applying multi-attribute group decision making (MAGDM) in construction project of both qualitative and quantitative approach was introduced by Mohammad et al., (1991), and found very successful for project management in Iranian construction project.

2.2 Related Literature

2.2.1 The Concept of Recruitment and Selection Strategies for International Construction Project

As indicated by Louw, G. J. (2013) recruitment is depicted as the arrangement of exercises and dealings used to lawfully get an adequate number of qualified individuals at the appropriate spot and time with the goal that the general public and the organization can choose each other in their own best short and long-haul interests. As such, the recruitment process gives the association a pool of conceivably qualified work applicants from which wise determination can be made to fill opportunities. Fruitful recruitment starts with appropriate business arranging and gauging. In this period of the staffing procedure, an association defines plans to fill or wipe out future employment opportunities dependent on an investigation of future needs, the ability accessible inside and outside of the company and the present and foreseen assets that can be extended to pull in and hold such ability. Additionally, identified with the achievement of recruitment procedure are the techniques a company is set up to utilize so as to recognize and choose the best possibility for its creating pool of HR (Brymer, R. An., et al., 2014).

Recruitment and selection process are important practices for international project and are crucial in affecting organizational success. Because of the way that companies are constantly fixed by data revolution to be increasingly forceful, it is natural to also consider utilizing this technology to re-organize the traditional recruitment and selection process through proper decision techniques, with that both the effectiveness and the efficiency of the processes can be increased and the quality of the recruitment and selection decision improved. A human resource information system (HRIS) outline is a framework neglected to get, store, control, examinations, recover, and appropriate related facts with respect to a company's HR (Purce, J. 2014). The purpose of the system is to support human resource services from the strategic level down to the tactical and operational levels. Numerous basic management matters, including recruitment and selection are thus included. The program inspires information related or modernized methods to take care of the problems and crucial significance as a forceful device in the records age (Low et al., 2004).

Researchers indicate that effective recruitment strategies for international projects and policies enable boards to find the best candidate for their organization. The personnel function becomes especially important when recruiting and selecting new administrators. A critical role for project manager and human resource management is how to elicit positive reactions from candidates when discussing administrative roles. At the point when beginnings are showed to workers to move towards vocations in organization (i.e., tapping shoulders of potential applicants), regularly a suspicious response occurs (Aluttis, C., et al., 2014). People without administrative experiences have negative perceptions and views of the role of the administrator. In attempts to attract and support individuals to the administrator's position it is necessary to identify what barriers prevent potential candidates from applying to the pool (Williams, C. 2013).

2.2.2 Recruitment and Selection Process for International Construction Project

Recruitment and selection frames a center piece of the focal exercises fundamental human resource management: to be specific, the procurement, improvement and reward of specialists. It much of the time shapes an essential piece of crafted by human resource supervisors or assigned pros inside work associations. In any case, and critically, recruitment and selection are frequently in light of

current circumstances taken by non-authorities, by the line administrators. There is, thusly, a critical sense in which it is the duty all things considered, and where HR offices exist, it might be that HR directors play even more a supporting warning job to those individuals who will administer or in different ways work with the new representative. Recruitment and selection likewise have an imperative task to carry out in assuring specialist performance and positive authoritative results. It is frequently definite that recruitment and selection of employees happens not simply to supplant leaving councils or add to a workforce but instead expects to set up specialists who can perform a formal and exhibit responsibility (Bratton, J., and Gold, J. 2017).

Sivertzen, A. M., et al., (2013) indicated that to be a high performing organization, human resource management must be able to assist the organization to place the right person in the right job. Incorporate recruitment, selection, position, assessment, preparing and advancement, pay and advantages, and maintenance of the workers of an association. Organizations have created human resource frameworks that help: (i) recruitment, selection, and hiring, (ii) job placement, (iii) performance appraisals, (iv) employee benefits analysis, (v) training and development, and (vi) health, safety, and security.

According to Ahmad, S. (2015) lists the essence of these in the following; build a pool of candidates for the job, have the applicants fill out application forms, utilize various selection techniques to identify viable job candidates, send at least one suitable employment contender to their manager, have the candidate(s) experience choice meetings, and decide to which candidate(s) an offer ought to be made. The first few activities of human resource management are recruiting and selecting which deal with the actions concerned, and the recruiting is less frequently alerted in human resource information system recently. Besides, e-recruitment on the web being the current trend for the recruitment and selection processes can further distinguish many activities of the processes.

Cania, L. (2014) indicated that the quality of new recruits depends upon an organization's recruitment strategies and that the relative effectiveness of the selection phase is inherently dependent upon the caliber of candidates attracted. Without a hesitation Van Dalen, H. P., et al., (2014) contends that the more successfully the registration organizes is done, the less imperative the genuine choice process progresses toward becoming. At the point when company settles on the choice to fill a current opening through staffing the main stage in the process includes leading an extensive employment scrutiny. This may already have been conducted through the human resource planning process, particularly where recruitment is a relatively frequent occurrence.

As indicated by Bryant, P. C., and Allen, D. G. (2013) one aftereffect of influential recruitment and selection is diminished work turnover and great characteristic spirit. Recruiting inadequately is exorbitant, since poor recruited people may perform seriously as well as leave their business, in this way requiring further recruitment. In a cross-national investigation of recruitment rehearses, recommends that, as a general rule, registration rehearses include next to zero endeavor to approve practices. Talent managers will in general depend on input from line supervisors and trial periods and disciplinary systems to remove failures.

Das, B. L., & Baruah, M. (2013) argues that recruitment sources are significantly linked to differences in employee performance, turnover, satisfaction and organizational commitment. In a survey of 201 large US companies, He further solicited respondents to rate the adequacy from nine recruitment sources in springy top mark, high-performing employees. The three best-positioned sources were representative referrals, school selecting and official hunt firms. However, in a study assessing the recruitment of new graduates, according to Rapp, T. L., et al., (2014) reiterated the anticipatory socialization stage for students planning to enter professions, and in particular the effects of recruitment and selection experiences on career expectations and orientation. They agreed that the nature of students' job search activity, the possession of relevant work experience, and exposure to employers through recruitment and selection activities may form part of the "evolving sequence of a person's work experiences" which contributes to anticipatory socialization.

Kramar, R. (2014) contended that giving employees more noteworthy attention to business openings, and outfitting them with the capacity to be active in moving toward potential managers will lead to more effective career self-management and selection processes. There is additionally proof that businesses favor graduates with a more extensive scope of abilities than simply scholastic learning and more noteworthy valuation for business needs the two of which can be increased through work understanding and consciousness of managers' recruitment and selection strategies. The attention on callings mirrors the desire that expectant socialization is probably going to be more noteworthy among these students. Although most students in their final years of university training will have had some contact with potential employers, students in dedicated professional courses are likely to be provided with information earlier in their training about potential employment in the profession. This is partly because of the prescribed nature of the degree; the mandatory post-degree training required for membership of the professional institute, unlike the problems identified in general degree courses, because lecturers are likely to have closer ties to the practicing profession (Rao, T. V. 2014).

2.2.3 The Selection Decision for International Construction Project

While the scale of applicant is dictated by the estimation of the recruitment way, the selection choice remains a troublesome one. Tracey, W. R. (2016) contends that most slip-ups are brought about by the way that executives by and large give little idea to the basic idea of the selection. Businesses are astounded and frustrated when an arrangement comes up short, and frequently the individual designated is accused instead of perceiving the shortcomings simultaneously and approach, even the soundest of actions and best practice (in determination) contain scope for mistake. A portion of this is because of the techniques themselves; however, the fundamental source is the delicacy of the human leaders. Selection tools accessible to companies can be portrayed along a continuum that ranges from the more conventional strategies for meetings, application structures and references, through to the more refined procedures that epitomize true to life information, inclination tests, evaluation focuses, work tests, psychological testing, etc.

2.2.4 Recruiting Sources/Methods

Specialists face numerous selections while choosing recruitment strategies. Issues to consider incorporate the kind of test cost, ease, member time requests and productivity. Professionals have various strategies from which to pick, including promoting, post office based mail and phone. Promoting can be utilized both to plug an examination and to select members. Recruitment by means of publicizing has the upsides of minimal effort and comfort, however the examples are non-irregular and frequently exceptionally energetic, and youth might be particularly difficult to achieve along these lines. Recruitment through mail is additionally low in expense and helpful, yet youth are hard to reach via mail and return rates will in general be low. An additional issue with mail asks for or reviews are that one can never be sure who finished the demand/overview (Cascio, W. F. 2014). Way to-entryway recruitment is another choice. For huge analyses, this recruitment technique can be exorbitant as far as staff time and travel costs, and it is hard to guarantee that spotters arbitrarily test homes. Regardless of these worries, way to-entryway recruitment might be an important recruitment method for certain potential members (Akingbola, K. 2013).

Lin, C., (2017) found that the number of people who refused to provide screening information tended to be higher by telephone than in person. However, refusals over the telephone tend to be less likely than with mailed surveys. It should be noted that telephone methods can be used not only for recruitment, but also for data collection. Recent advances in telephone survey methodology have made telephone recruitment and surveying an increasingly attractive option in many research fields. Other systems, such as computer-assisted telephone interview programs, are used in marketing research and can be adapted for telephone recruiting and data collection in studies requiring specific samples.

CHAPTER THREE

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This chapter deals with the methodology adopted in conducting the study. The chapter is organized as follows; research design, sources of data, population and sampling, research instrument (data collection technique), administration of instrument and analysis of data. Research is something that people undertake in order to find out things in a systematic manner, thereby increasing their knowledge. It is noted that this definition captures two significant phrases: “systematic way” and “to find out things”. “Systematic” suggest that research is based on logical relationships and not just beliefs (Saunders and Thornhill, 2009). It depicts the accurate thought the researcher is completing (William, 2001).

3.1 Research Design

Research design is used for different types of research which a researcher wants to explore. Research design provides a complete guidance and way to do effective and efficient research guideline for conducting a research. It also covered the whole techniques of research methodology that is used for research investigation. As per (Crotty, 1998; Fowler (1995) research design is helpful for investigating the research problem and identifying the relationship between variables. The descriptive research design was used for investigation of this research and qualitative and quantitative research methods were used to analyze the results through SPSS and semi-structured interviews. The study used instrument and interview question was gathering a data and all the respondents’ response was good while data collection.

3.2 Research Setting

The present study was cross-sectional, and data is gathered from the capital city of Bangladesh. The study scope was limited because of time constraints and limited resources. Data was collected from construction industry employees of Bangladesh who are working in Chinese companies.

3.3 Sources of Data

Primary data were used in conducting the research.

3.3.1 Primary Sources

The present study gathered data through primary source with the help of questionnaire and semi-structured interviews. Close-ended questionnaire given to the respondents in their work place and got response because close-ended questions were used such as Frankfort-Nachmias, C., & Nachmias, D. (1996), as cited in Adu-Darkoh, M. (2014). In order to maintain the ethics of research, all the data is original and collected from respondents in real time and natural environment. In order to collect reliable and valid information, the researcher contacted employees of the Human resource department of the construction companies in Dhaka Bangladesh. Data acquired was investigated utilizing SPSS to get significant conclusions and proposals.

3.3.2 Questionnaires

In order to determine the perception of different employees in Chinese construction companies of Bangladesh regarding recruitment and selection the employees for international project. The questionnaire was adapted from the previous study of (Pinto, J.K. and Slevin, D.P. 2016). Questionnaire structured into sub parts for data collection. Section A had questions to determine the respondents' background. Section B was to design to get the opinions of recruiting the employees in international project. Before the questionnaires were emailed to our respondents in international companies, a pilot study was conducted in Bangladesh to test the validity of the questions and if they will be suitable to meet the research objectives. We distributed the questionnaires to employees working in international projects. For the quantitative method of research, the questions were design based on the 5-point Likert Scale, which measures from 1-5 according to the level of contribution and impact of each factor.

Strongly Agree (5)

Agree (4)

Neutral (3)

Disagree (2)

Strongly Disagree (1)

A pilot study involves testing a questionnaire with a small group of people who represents target respondents. This will help pin point mistakes in the questionnaire and will also determine if the questions will be understood and easily answered by the respondents. A pilot study was conducted in Bangladesh. We had the opportunity to meet some employees who took some time to study the questionnaires and gave some feedback. The feedbacks obtained were as followed;

- The questionnaires must have cover page
- The sections in the questionnaires should contain general information about the respondents.
- Some questions needed to be modified including more details
- Some questions were repeated having the same meaning
- Use simple words to ease understanding of the questions.

The feedbacks back were then noted and the questionnaires modified and adjusted accordingly. A total of 100 questionnaires were prepared and distributed through personal visits to employees in construction companies of Bangladesh. Semi-structured interviews were also conducted with some employees to get their opinions on recruitment and selection strategies for recruiting staff in international projects.

3.3.3 Interviews

According to Kvale, S., & Brinkmann, S. (2009) interviews is conducting for qualitative research method. There are three types of interview techniques had developed by previous researchers. The first technique is structured interview, which is formally designed for data collection, and questions are fixed set of responses. The second technique is semi-structured interview which is also designed for data collection and covered the set of general topic. The third techniques are un-structured interview which is informal designed and ask any question according to the relevant topic. Semi-structured interview been chosen to conduct the research.

3.4 Questionnaire and Semi-Structured Interview Development Process

First, I made adapted the questionnaire from pervious study, went to some construction project companies in Bangladesh, and gathered data from the respondents. The questionnaire is consisted of open and close ended questions which asked from the employees. A semi-structured interview outline is also developed for interviews from the international projects companies in Bangladesh. Firstly, I used this outline

Style: open-ended questions to get lengthy and descriptive answers rather than close-ended questions (those that can be answered with “yes” or “no”).

Language: I used terms that participants can understand, given their knowledge, language skills, cultural background, age, gender, etc. Be mindful of the social or cultural contexts of your questions.

Concise: I keep the questions as short and specific as possible. Avoid asking two-in-one questions, such as, “Do you travel by car and by bike?”

Frame: I avoid questions with a strong positive or negative association. Avoid phrasing questions as negatives (e.g., “How don’t you like to get to work?”).

3.5 Reliability Test

The reliability is the main factor, which was measured through statistical packages for social sciences (SPSS) software. If the instrument reliability is greater than $\alpha = .07$ it is acceptable in social sciences study and data is valid overall, if the reliability is less than $\alpha = .06$ the questionnaire is not reliable and valid for the research investigation, so this result is tested before a researcher data collection through pilot testing, the pilot testing and reliability of the questionnaire is good overall and gather than $\alpha = .07$. Reliability study is essential to lead any examination. It depends on the restricted example of the exploration examine. It encourages the professional to look at the reliability and validity of the instruments, which he can use in his investigation plans. The results of Cronbach's alpha, is .821 overall. Which shows questionnaire is valid for data collection.

3.6 Sampling Techniques

Simple random sampling and convenience sampling technique were taken to collect data from the staff of international companies. This is essential that the populace will have an equivalent shot of being chosen. Significantly, the purposive sampling technique, which is a non-probability sampling technique, was used to select respondents who deal directly with recruitment and selection in international project management.

3.7 Population

A populace is characterized as all components (people, objects and events) that meet the criteria for consideration in a study (Burns, N., & Grove, S. K. 1993). Construction industry was chosen for the study. The number of inhabitants in the study comprised of representatives from the HR division of the construction companies.

3.8 Sample Size

Sample is the sub part of population, which is denoted by (n) (Miller, D. C., & Salkind, N. J. 2002). A sample size of 100 was chosen from the selected departments for the study. This was based on the staff strength of the various departments and to ensure that the sampled was representative enough to draw conclusion.

The following formula (Kish equation) was utilized to decide the sample size:

$$n = \frac{n'}{1 + \frac{n'}{N}}$$

Where:

N=the number of total people

n = the sample size gained from the finite population

n' = the sample size gained from infinite population = $\frac{S^2}{V^2}$; where S^2 is the variance of the population elements and V is a standard error of sampling population. (Usually S=0.5 and V=0.06). So

$$n' \frac{S^2}{V^2} = \frac{0.5^2}{0.06^2} = \frac{0.25}{0.0036} = 69.44$$

According to Kish (1965), it demonstrated that the sample size could be determined as the accompanying condition for 94% confident level:

So, for 100 Populations:

N=100

$$n = \frac{69.44}{1 + \frac{69.44}{100}} = 41$$

This implies the questionnaire ought to be appropriated to 41 workers of the HR division to accomplish 94% confident level.

3.9 Data Collection Instrument

There are different sources for data collection. The present study used instrument for data collection as well as semi-structured interviews has been taken by the researcher. The instrument is valid and reliable for data collection and tested through Cronbach's alpha, which is considerable for data gathering. The study adapts the questionnaire from the previous study of scholars which they already done on the recruitment and selection strategies for recruiting staff in international projects.

3.10 Administration of Instruments

Questionnaire has been conveyed among the respondents at their work places and collected when they finished and properly filled all the questionnaire items. The 115 questionnaires are distributed and 100 questionnaires are collected in complete filling. The discard rate of questionnaire was 15 due to incomplete and improper filling by the respondents.

3.11 Data Analysis

According to the (Hays, W. L. 1973) statistical method was utilized on the grounds that it is the best instrument to recognize, analyze, reach a conclusion. The data has been analyzed through SPSS 23.0 software in the form of different tables, charts and percentage.

Chapter Four

Data Analysis

This chapter explains information gathered from the field through the use of questionnaires. These are analyzed to emphasize response from respondents using various forms of graphical representations. This chapter is also divided into sub-headings to throw more light on questions asked on the field. The first part deals with the demographic variables of respondents and the second part discuss the result of the interview, which took by the researcher.

4.1 Demographic Variables

On demographic data, questions were asked on gender, academic qualifications and number of years at the post. From the sample size, hundred respondents were selected from the international project management companies in Bangladesh.

Gender of Respondents

Table 4.1: Gender of Respondents

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Male	87	87.0	87.0	87.0
Female	13	13.0	13.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

From table 4.1, it is realized that 87 of respondents representing 87% of the total number of participants were males while 13 representing 13% of the total number were females. This demonstrates there were marginally more male members than female in this survey and it might be because of the inspecting method utilized in choosing respondents or that the organization has more male laborers than females.

Education of Respondents

This was to find out the highest education of the various respondents in the study area; responses are as follows;

Table 4.2: Education Level of Respondents

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Graduate	53	53.0	53.0	53.0
Masters	46	46.0	46.0	99.0
HND	1	1.0	1.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.2 shows that four respondents had graduate degrees, while 53 had graduate degrees and 46 respondents had a master's degree in various field of study. From the table, it is realized that the international project companies have several levels of qualified personnel to help carry out the day to day activities of the institution.

Experience of Respondents

This was to find out the number of years respondents had spent at their work post; answers are illustrated as follows;

Table 4.3: Experience of Respondents

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Less than 1 year	41	41.0	41.0	41.0
1 – 6 years	51	51.0	51.0	92.0
7 – 12 years	6	6.0	6.0	98.0
13 – 18 years	2	2.0	2.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.3 shows that employees had 1-6 years of experience to manage an international project of international companies which represent 51% of the sample size. While employees have less than 1 years of experience in handling the process of hiring a project manager for different international projects. Only a few employees had 7-12 years of experience in managing human resource strategies for project management in international companies.

4.2 Important Recruitment Strategies for Hiring Employees

These are some recruitment and selection strategies questions were asked to the respondents who already worked in international projects and want to recruit more human resource in their project. Some questions are related to the quantitative method, and the Likert scale from 1 strongly disagree to 5 strongly agree used for measuring the response of respondents. The quantitative response has been measured through software statistical packages for social sciences (SPSS 23.0). The results of the quantitative method are analyzed via a test of frequency distribution and found the participation result of respondents for recruitment staff in an international project. So, all the questions description is discussed below;

Table 4.4: Conducting Interview of the employees

Question No 1

Which managers are best placed to conduct interviews? (You can select more multiple)

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
HR Manager	22	22.0	22.0	22.0
Project Manager	78	78.0	78.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Which managers are best placed to conduct interviews? (You can select more multiple)

Figure 4.1: Conducting Interview of the employees

The first question asked to the respondents during the interview that which managers are best placed to conduct interviews for hiring employees in international project management. The highest response shows that 78 (78%) respondent's want project manager for conducting interviews of employees. 22 (22%) respondents said that the HR manager is the best person for conducting interviews of employees in an international project.

Table 4.5: Company's policy in recruitment and selection

Question No 2

Your company has any formal policy for the recruitment and selection of project team members for international projects.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Disagree	4	4.0	4.0	4.0
Neutral	10	10.0	10.0	14.0
Agree	28	28.0	28.0	42.0
Strongly Agree	58	58.0	58.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Your company has any formal policy for the recruitment and selection of project team members for international projects.

Figure 4.2: Company's policy in recruitment and selection

Table 4.5 shows that the result of question 2 which asked the respondents regarding any company formal policy for the recruitment and selection of project team members for international projects. 58 (58%) respondents are strongly agreed on that question during the interview and said they have a good and formal policy for hiring the project team members for international projects. 28 (28%) respondents agree with this statement, and 10 (10%) respondents are neutral who did not give any answer on that question.

Question No 3

The job vacancies made open to the public.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Neutral	12	12.0	12.0	12.0
Agree	21	21.0	21.0	33.0
Strongly Agree	67	67.0	67.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Figure 4.3: Job Vacancies made public or not

Table 4.6 shows that the response of employees whenever job vacancies made its open for the public and anyone can apply through proper channel because we have an online portal and we received an application through online for recruitment of project management team. Sometimes we have already team members in our companies. Through the interview, the 67 (67%) respondents strongly agreed on the interview question that job vacancies are open for everyone. 21 (21%) respondents are agreed and only (12%) respondents are neutral on that interview question.

Table 4.7: Opportunities for would be team members

Question No 4

Your company provides equal opportunities for all would-be (potential) project team members when it comes to recruitment and selection.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Disagree	3	3.0	3.0	3.0
Neutral	2	2.0	2.0	5.0
Agree	26	26.0	26.0	31.0
Strongly Agree	69	69.0	69.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Your company provide equal opportunities for all would-be (potential) project team members when it comes to recruitment and selection.

Figure 4.4: Opportunities for would be team members

Table 4.7 shows that the response of respondents regarding the company environment that the company provides equal opportunities for all would be potential project team members when it comes to recruitment and selection. 69 (69%) respondents strongly agree that company is already providing equal opportunities to all employees who are working in different international projects for many years. 2 (2%) respondents are neutral and don't want to give this answer in detail, and 26 (26%) respondents are agreed on that question statement concerning equal opportunities for all team members.

Table 4.8: Recruiting the locals and internationals

Question No 5

Both local and international team members are given equal consideration during the recruitment process.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Disagree	2	2.0	2.0	2.0
Neutral	22	22.0	22.0	24.0
Agree	23	23.0	23.0	47.0
Strongly Agree	53	53.0	53.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Both local and international team members are given equal consideration during the recruitment process.

Figure 4.5: Recruiting the locals and internationals

Table 4.8 shows the response of respondents about equal opportunities for local and international team members during the recruitment process for an international project. 53 (53%) respondents are strongly agreed with this statement that whenever we recruit local and international team members for a specific project, we provide equal opportunities and incentives. 23 (23%) respondents are agreed with the question during the interview and few 22 (22%) respondents given neutral response while interviewing.

Table 4.9: Consideration of existing employees

Question No 6

When vacancies occur, are existing project team members considered?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Disagree	7	7.0	7.0	7.0
Neutral	9	9.0	9.0	16.0
Agree	62	62.0	62.0	78.0
Strongly Agree	22	22.0	22.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Figure 4.6: Consideration of existing employees

Table 4.9 shows that the response of respondents for recruitment team members in an international project. 62 (62%) respondents said that when vacancies are announced existing team members also considered for recruitment in international project. Sometimes they don't have capable human resource then we recruitment international team members for managing international project. 22 (22%) respondents are also strongly agreed with this statement, and 9 (9%) respondents are given a neutral response to that interview question.

Question No 7

Your company's human resources policies allow employees to secure promotions when they are assigned to projects.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Disagree	2	2.0	2.0	2.0
Neutral	14	14.0	14.0	16.0
Agree	40	40.0	40.0	56.0
Strongly Agree	44	44.0	44.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Figure 4.7: Promotions during the projects

Table 4.10 shows that the response of respondents regarding the company human resources policies which allow employees to secure promotions when they are assigned to another project. 44 (44%) respondents are strongly agreed that company HR policy allows us to secure our promotion if we performed well in an international project as manager and team member. 40 (40%) respondents are also agreed with the statement of this interview question, and 14(14%) respondents are neutral on that statement about the human resource promotion policy in the company.

Table 4.11: Retention of the employees

Question No 8

If a project is over, are the employees retained?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Yes	86	86.0	86.0	86.0
No	14	14.0	14.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.11 shows that the response of respondents after completion of the project. 86 (86%) respondents say yes they are retained after the completion of the project and 14 (14%) respondents say no they are not retained after the completion of the project because they recruited only for that international project.

Table 4.12: Placements after a project

Question No 9

At the end of the project, will these permanent employees go back to the positions they held before they were given the project.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Yes	86	86.0	86.0	86.0
No	14	14.0	14.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.12 shows that after that end of the project permanent employees go back to the positions they held before the project. The 86 (14%) respondents say yes they go back to their positions after the end of the local and international project. 14 (14%) respondents say that they are working on a contract so whenever the project is ended there contract is also finished, and they go back home.

Table 4.13: Analysis before advertising vacancies

Question No 10

Your company outlines job analysis (i.e. duties, responsibilities, skills etc. required for particular projects) before advertising vacancies for projects.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Disagree	3	3.0	3.0	3.0
Neutral	4	4.0	4.0	7.0
Agree	74	74.0	74.0	81.0
Strongly Agree	19	19.0	19.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Figure 4.8: Analysis before advertising vacancies

Table 4.13 shows that the result of the company outlines job analysis which deals the duties, responsibilities, skills for a particular project before advertising the vacancies for international projects. 74 (74%) respondents are agreed with the statement that job analysis outline and advertising is required before recruiting the team members for the international project. 19 (19%) respondents are also agreed with the question that it is necessary for hiring the human resource in international or national project.

Table 4.14: Skills that company looks for

Question No 11

What are some skills your company looks for during project team recruitment? (You can select more multiple)

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Technological expertise	16	16.0	16.0	16.0
Credibility	64	64.0	64.0	80.0
Local and Political connections	20	20.0	20.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

**What are some skills your company looks for during project team recruitment?
(You can select more multiple)**

Figure 4.9: Skills those companies look for

Table 4.14 shows that some skills which company looks for during the recruitment of team members in international projects. The best skill a company looks for a team member is availability which shows the maximum response of respondents during the interview. After that, a company looks a person who has good technological expertise with problem-solving ability. A company also determines the credibility and local and political connection of person before recruiting in international projects.

Table 4.15: Important factor for recruitment

Question No 12

Which of these factor(s) for recruitment and selection of project team members are regarded as most important? (You can select more multiple)

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Academic qualifications	33	33.0	33.0	33.0
Work experience	20	20.0	20.0	53.0
Interview	41	41.0	41.0	94.0
Test	6	6.0	6.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Which of these factor(s) for recruitment and selection of project team members are regarded as most important? (You can select more multiple)

Figure 4.10: Important factor for recruitment

Table 4.15 shows that factors which are most important for recruitment and selection of project team members in international projects. 20 (20%) respondents said that work experience is the most important factor for the recruitment of team members because if a person has the experience to handle project he can easily manage the project in time. 33 (33%) respondents said that academic qualification also does matter in recruitment and selection process of team member and 41 (41%) respondents said that interview is also an important factor for recruitment and selection of team members in project management.

Table 4.16: Methods of recruiting

Question No 13

Which of these methods is applicable for project team members' recruitment in your Company?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Advertisement	21	21.0	21.0	21.0
Employee referrals	73	73.0	73.0	94.0
Employment agencies	6	6.0	6.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Which of these methods is applicable for project team members' recruitment in your Company?

Figure 4.11: Methods of recruiting

Table 4.16 shows which methods are more applicable for project team member recruitment in the company. 73 (73%) respondents said that employee referrals in the most applicable method for recruitment of team member in the project. 21 (21%) respondents said that advertisement is also an important factor for hiring team member in a project and only 6 (6%) respondents said that employment agencies also played a vital role during recruitment and selection of team member in a project.

Table 4.17: Dependency on agencies for recruitment

Question No 14

Your company relies on any agent(s) and recruitment agencies for the recruitment and selection of employees in the company.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Disagree	1	1.0	1.0	1.0
Neutral	10	10.0	10.0	11.0
Agree	33	33.0	33.0	44.0
Strongly Agree	56	56.0	56.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Figure 4.12: Dependency on agencies for recruitment

Table 4.17 shows that a company relied on any agents for recruitment agencies for the recruitment and selection of employees for an international project. 56 (56%) respondents are strongly agreed with the statement of question that company also relies on the recruitment agencies for the recruitment and selection of team member in the project. 33 (33%) respondents are also agreed with the statement, and 10 (10%) respondents are given a neutral response on that interview question.

4.3 Qualitative Results

These are some interview questions, which asked the respondents regarding the recruitment and selection strategies for hiring staff in international projects, and content analysis has been used for interview questions. The semi-structured interviews were taken from the respondents on their workplace and answers are discussed below;

Interview Question No 15

At your company, all the recruitment activities are managed centrally, or will each project team manage its hiring?

Answer

The company activities are managed by the CEO and Owner of the company through a centralized system. The entire departments are working separately and directly reporting to the general manager and CEO of the company. It depends on the nature of the project sometime project duration is short term, and sometimes project duration is long term. When project duration is short term then each project team manage its own hiring when the project is long term then company and project team is involved in the process of recruitment and selection of team member in project.

Interview Question No 16

What are some of the challenges that your company associated with while recruitment and selection practices of project team members for international projects?

Answer

There are some challenges associated with the recruitment and selection practices of project team members for an international project. Because a company needs a capable human resource for its international project and they have to do all job analysis practices, which are time taking process for recruitment and selection of team members. Sometimes we did not find a suitable candidate for managing the project due to lack of experience and education. A language is also a barrier while the recruitment of team members for an international project because they cannot coordinate properly regarding the project details.

Interview Question No 17

What factors will improve recruitment and selection strategies at your company for any specific project?

Answer

I think many factors can improve the recruitment and selection strategies for the company. First of all, education, experience does matter which can helpful in recruitment appropriate human resource or team members for any local and international project. Proper advertisement and employee referrals are also an important factor to improve the recruitment and selection in a company. Other challenges are also facing recruitment and selection process at international project company's the availability of key talents in the job market for specialized areas within the company because company and institution need key talents to help run the company and that is quite difficult to find in the job market. Another challenge facing a company in its recruitment and selection processes is competition from other institutions. It is also explained that financial companies in the country are springing up fast, and they are all recruiting the best to stay on top.

Interview Question No 18

What measures will have to be taken to keep talents who are in high demand on the market inside the company?

Answer

There are factors that can help improve recruitment and selection strategies for recruitment and selection of team members in international projects. A company must be emphasized and advertised vacancies early and must be detailed enough for prospective applicants to assess themselves whether they can do the job required of them. The company also explained the job requirements and its relevant experience must be adopted in the selection of recruits which cost little and more so time-saving as such people spends little or no time during orientation. The company also explained that the department not solely relies on the qualification and experience but lifestyle and background of all would be employees must be checked to make sure the best is being recruited for the company. In addition, another important thing is, the recruits should be given better training, opportunities and salary.

CHAPTER FIVE

FINDINGS and DISCUSSION

5.1 Discussion

The study investigated the recruitment and selection strategies for international construction projects in Bangladesh. The respondents are agreed on all the recruitment and selection strategies for recruiting the team member in an international project. The study findings also established that the recruitment and selection strategies are applicable for the project team members. The findings of the study also demonstrate that the project manager and human resource manager should be placed for the recruitment of team members in the company. The study results indicated that recruitment of team members, forecast impacts were analyzed; prepare job description by experience. It is also shown from the findings that academic qualification, test, experience, and interview had a positive impact on the recruitment and selection strategies.

From the results, it is also revealed that the respondents were agreed on the most important factors for recruitment of project team member is advertisement, employee referrals, and recruitment agencies. The study established that the top management support was the most important factor in the successful implementation in the recruitment and selection process in every company. The study also revealed that the experience of the project management staff, training of earned value

management also plays an important role in the successful implementation in recruitment and selection of project team member. The study demonstrates that the simplification of the recruitment procedure, the maturity of the company's project management system as important factors. The study established that the retention and improper advertisement was the biggest challenge in deploying human resource management in the projects.

The findings also revealed that the need for an experienced and talented project manager who can manage the all recruitment and selection process effectively and efficiently. The study also demonstrates that the improved estimating and planning to recruit team member in an international project, early preparing, and advertising is the advantage for the company. The study also suggests that the project manager should make sure to plan for recruitment meetings schedules regularly to discuss the new hiring along within the budget allocation and timeframe. The present study supported the previous finding of (Ballantyne, I. 2009) which investigated that proper recruitment and selection for the international project has a significant impact in the construction sector of Bangladesh. As per finding (Miyake, D. 2002), recruitment and selection strategies for recruiting team members in international project management has positively associated with the development of the construction sector in Bangladesh.

The findings of this study are in tandem with existing information in the literature that recruitment and selection criteria for international projects have a significant effect on companies output. According to Huselid (2014) observed that recruitment and selection strategies have a significant impact on the international project management due to the arrangement of a vast pool of qualified candidates: matched with a dependable and legitimate determination it has a considerable impact over the quality and sort of abilities new employees have. Similarly, Gamage (2014) noted that the recruitment and selection strategies would determine who is hired, shapes employee behavior and attitude. If appropriately structured, it will distinguish capable applicants and precisely match them to the job. According to (Rauf 2015; Terpstra and Rozell 2013) there is a positive association between the extensiveness of recruiting, selection test validation and the use of formal selection procedures, organizations performance and firm profits. Rauf (2015) further investigated that

sophisticated recruitment and selection procedures are positively related to performance in organizations. Accordingly, Okoh (2014), not just that organizational selection strategies determine who is hired, the utilization of the best possible determination criteria will expand the likelihood that the ideal individual will be picked. At the point when the best individuals are chosen for the activity, efficiency increases (Osemeke, 2012).

Research Question Answer 1

1. Which medium should Chinese companies use to recruit employees for their projects in Bangladesh?

Answer: Recruitment may be conducted in international projects internally through the promotion and transfer of existing personnel or through referrals, by current staff members, of friends and family members. Where internal recruitment is the picked technique for filling vacancies, employment opportunities can be promoted by job posting, that is, a strategy of placing notices on manual and electronic bulletin boards, in company newsletters and through office memoranda. Referrals are normally informal notices that are an ease for every contract method for selecting. Internal recruitment does not always produce the number or quality of personnel needed; in such an instance, the organization needs to recruit from external sources, either by encouraging walk-in applicants; advertising vacancies in newspapers, magazines and journals, and the visual and/or audio media; using employment agencies to “head hunt”; advertising on-line via the Internet; or through job fairs and the use of college recruitment. Public service agencies are also can be helpful for hiring employees in international project and these agencies enjoy greater exposure to scrutiny than most private sector organizations; therefore, openness and transparency in recruitment and selection practices are crucial. The discussion that follows will identify some of the options available for attracting applicants to the public service job market and discuss strategies for managing the process.

The medium of recruitment might be directed in worldwide activities inside through the advancement and exchange of existing work force or through referrals, by current staff individuals,

friends and family members. Where interior recruitment is the chosen technique for filling opportunities, employment openings can be promoted by work posting, that is, a practice of setting sees on manual and electronic poster sheets, in organization brochures and through office memoranda. Referrals are generally oral advertisements that are an ease for each contract method for recruiting. Interior recruitment does not generally deliver the number or nature of staff required; in such an occasion, the company needs to select from outside sources, either by empowering stroll in candidates; dissemination opportunities in papers, magazines and diaries, and the visual or potentially sound media; utilizing work organizations to "head chase"; promoting on-line by means of the internet; or through employment fairs and the utilization of school recruitment. Public management offices are additionally can be useful for recruiting employees in global projects and these offices appreciate more prominent introduction to investigation than most private sector company's; consequently, accessibility and straightforwardness in recruitment and selection strategies are significant. The discussion that pursues will differentiate a share of the selection accessible for pulling in candidates to the public service work platform and talk about strategies for dealing with the technique.

Posting Vacancies

As demonstrated before job posting mentions on the act of publicizing an open work to employees (frequently by truly posting it on announcement areas) and posting its properties, for example, criteria of learning, capability, ability and experience. The reason for presenting opening is on convey to the consideration of every single intrigued individual (inside or out of the company) the employments that are to be filled.

Recruiting from internal sources

There are sound purposes behind selecting from sources inside the company: The ability of the recruiting employees is known so it is anything but difficult to survey potential for the following dimension. On the other hand, assessments of outdoor recruited people depend on less solid sources, for example, references, and generally concise experiences, for example, interviews.

Recruiting from external sources

The other source of recruiting techniques can be gathered into two classes: informal and formal. Informal selecting strategies tap a littler market than formal techniques. These strategies may incorporate rehiring previous employees and browsing among those walk in applicants whose unstructured list of qualifications had been held on document. The utilization of referrals likewise comprises a casual employing strategy.

On-Line Applications/Recruiting on the Internet

Utilizing the Internet is quicker and less expensive than numerous conventional strategies for selecting. Jobs can be posted on web sites for an modest sum (not exactly in the print media), stay there for times of thirty or sixty days or more - at no extra expense - and are accessible twenty-four hours every day. Candidates can see itemized data about the activity and the company and afterward reply electronically.

Job fairs

The idea of job fair is to bring those keen on getting a new line of work into those organizations that are looking for applicants. Job fairs are open for at which businesses can show the best their organizations bring to the table with the goal that activity searchers can settle on educated decisions. They are viewed as a standout amongst the best ways for work seekers to get jobs.

Maintaining fairness/equity in the recruitment process

Usually hard to guarantee and look after fairness/value in the recruitment method in spite of the fact that, in each ward, there are laws that shield people and helpless groups from the distrustful

effect of unfair practices. Where important, frameworks, point by point strategies and procedures exist or should be set up to limit separation.

Research Question Answer 2

2. How should Chinese companies select their employees for their international projects in Bangladesh?

Answers: This is the criteria for selecting staff in international project.

Curriculum vitas / resumes and written applications

A curriculum vitae (CV) / resume provide valuable information relating to a person's professional qualification captions and experience. All information in the CV should be verified where appropriate (e.g., asking applicants to explain gaps in employment history). Requesting job applicants to address specific selection criteria (i.e., essential and desirable) can improve the efficiency of reviewing CVs.

Conducting interviews

Structured interviews are recommended. A structured interview involves asking each candidate the same set of questions and assessing their responses by pre-determined criteria. Questions and assessment criteria should be based on accurate, updated job descriptions. It is also helpful to develop criteria to categories responses (e.g., as excellent, good, average and unsatisfactory). An interview panel consisting of a representative selection of people may also be helpful. Two common types of structured interview questions are:

- Situational questions which ask candidates about hypothetical scenarios that may be encountered in the job and how they would respond in that situation.
- Experienced-based questions which focus on specific examples of the candidate's prior work experiences and their responses to past situations that are relevant to the job in question.

Reference checks

Referees are useful for identifying past employment problems and clarifying the accuracy of information presented in an interview or CV. Only a small percentage of all reference checks are negative, therefore, it is often difficult to differentiate between candidates on the basis of reference checks alone.

5.2 Summary of Findings

The following are the major findings from the study:

5.2.1 Recruitment Process and Selection Strategies for International Project

The whole recruitment process can be described as follows.

Figure 5.1: Recruitment Process

Advertising is usual for recruitment in an international project as well as job vacancies, while a few candidates are now and again recruited by listening in on others' conversations, through existing employees (worker referrals). Other than being less expensive, individuals contracted by listening in on others discussions remain longer since they have a clearer thought of what the activity includes.

Most respondents shared this assertion with regards to recruitment and selection strategies for international projects. The research revealed that the international company's policy or practice on recruiting and selection was based on several units; the first is the internal recruitment and invitations from applicants from the public. The first is an analysis of the various departments to find out if there are vacancies to be filled. The various departments search within its staff to find competent members to fill job vacancies. When that fails employee referrals are used where employees are allowed to recommend potential employees for the various departments. The second stage is where the company source for employees through agencies that helps in recruiting people for the international project.

The other is through the general advertisement in the dailies where the overall population would all be able to apply for the positions accessible. Shortlisted candidates are then welcomed for a meeting and consequent selection. A portion of the strategies utilized in recruiting and selection of workers are through employee's referrals, professional workplaces, proficient affiliations and advertisements in the different dailies. The investigation likewise exposed that all organizations had systematized methods for selecting new workers. The first is that potential employees must have the fundamental or right instructive foundation before they meet all requirements for a meeting which is the following stage once a planned worker is shortlisted. Arranging and introduction is the following stage if an individual is recruited or selected.

5.2.2 Effectiveness of Recruitment and Selection Strategies for International Project

The investigation agreed that the respondent's view about recruitment and selection strategies were extremely viable as the right material is constantly used; most of respondents trusted that these strategies were great. It also shows that respondents agreed that these measures were effective. The other indifferent or trusted that these measures were not viable and the reasons raised included partiality and inclination towards potential employees. All the more so it was understood that variables, for example, work experience, education, interviews and test utilized in selecting employees make the selecting and recruitment arrangements successful in choosing the best for the development international projects.

5.2.3 Ways to Improve Recruitment and Selection Strategies for International Project

The analysis revealed that international project companies have methods and systems with respect to recruiting and selecting of workers; coming up next were given to help enhance such practices. Respondents said that the technique for recruiting and selecting must to be entirely pursued to guarantee that the right applicants are accommodated the organization. Organizations, for example, educational competence, experience, and interviews all assistance select the best of possibility for the organization. All the more in this way, it was understood that equivalent open doors ought to be given to all candidates who apply for employments for an international projects to help guarantee decency in the selection method and not to hand others an undue preferred standpoint over others. Besides, it was understood that to make the selection and recruitment method complete abilities must to be focused and should to likewise be connected with the activity to be done as most qualification do not much the job to be finished.

The present study has some implication for recruitment and selection of human resource in international project. The study is helpful for international firms who want to recruit human resource for their international project. International project companies could adopt these recruitment and selection strategies for recruiting staff. The present study is helpful for national and international companies who want to hire employees for different short- and long-term international projects. This study focused on the construction sector of Bangladesh and identified some recruitment and selection strategies for hiring staff in international project.

5.3 Suggestions

There are some suggestions that are found in the results. Recruitment and selection in any international project is a serious business as the success of any company or efficiency in service delivery depends on the quality of its workforce who was recruited into the company through recruitment and selection strategies. It is also found that for the recruitment of staff in international project applicants should have previous sound experience of handling project related tasks. The

study suggested that for recruitment in international projects, a company should evaluate the qualification and previous record of the employees. It is also important for project managers to understand the objectives, policies, and practices used for selection. More importantly, those in charge of settling on determination choices ought to have adequate information whereupon to base their choices. The company's human resource policies and practices represent important forces for shaping employee behavior and attitudes. Given the findings, the study suggests that in designing and instituting recruitment and selection strategies quality should not be compromised. Therefore, the present study suggested that companies should be focused on experience and qualified persons for recruiting in an international project.

5.4 Limitations

Project management is rather a new field of management science and its developing. Not many studies have been done, especially in recruitment strategies for project. There is an extreme lack of literature while it comes to recruitment strategies for projects. This research is conducted in Bangladesh, which is a developing country. So, the findings from this study might not appropriate for developed countries. The respondents of this study are currently working in the construction projects. Therefore, these findings might be helpful for other projects but might not be fully appropriate.

Chapter Six

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The purpose of this chapter is to round off the study with a conclusion, the implication of the study and recommendations. The conclusions would be made from the analysis and the objectives of the research.

6.1 Conclusion

The project construction sector is one of the most important economic sectors in Bangladesh. The present study discussed the recruitment and selection strategies for international projects from which recruitment of team members in international project. The main objective of the study is to

investigating the recruitment and selection strategies for employees in international project by taking the interview of 50 respondents who already involved in international project management. The questionnaire has been distributed among the employees and asked question related to the recruitment and selection strategies for international project. The output of the study revealed that there are many strategies are effective and suitable to recruit and select the human resource for construction international projects. The present study will be determined on the future need of human resource in construction projects and corrective action can be taken to minimize any adverse impact on project performance. This research will help to recruit and select the team members in construction international projects and thus reduce their effects. The investigation uncovered that international project companies have arrangements and methodologies concerning recruiting and selections of workers, coming up next were given to help enhance such practices. Respondents expressed that the method for recruitment & selection ought to be carefully followed so as to guarantee that the correct materials are accommodated the organization. All the more along these lines, it was understood that equivalent opportunities ought to be given to all candidates who apply for occupations for international projects to help guarantee the fairness in the selection procedure and not to hand others undue preferred standpoint over others. Additionally, it was understood that to make the selection procedure and enrollment system complete, qualifications ought to be pushed and ought to likewise be connected with the job to be done.

6.2 Recommendations

From the study it is understood that recruitment and selection strategies for construction international project is of great importance to every company, though an integral part of human resource planning and development, its application and operation and challenges makes its strategies quite difficult. These recommendations are therefore made to help make these strategies more effective. All applicants must be treated fairly; issues of favoritism should be avoided while giving the chance to all. Employee referrals though a good idea should be minimized to cater for a certain number of people rather than a whole scale opportunity. That gives room to favoritism and at times employment of individuals who might not contribute meaningfully to organizational output. The project manager and human resource manager should appraise employees to help them give off their best and help improve performance of employees; this will always keep employees

on their toes to give off their best. Refresher courses must be organized for employees for them to be abreast with trends in the ever-growing market. It was revealed in the analysis that key talents are difficult to come by, the company can help upgrade the skills of some of its staff in areas they find difficult to recruit in the market. This will also go a long way to help staff contribute to the success of the company.

6.3 Implication of the study

The present study has some implication for recruitment and selection of human resource in international project. The study is helpful for international firms who want to recruit human resource for their international project. International project companies could adopt these recruitment and selection strategies for recruiting staff. The present study is helpful for national and international companies who want to hire employees for different short- and long-term international projects. This study focused on the construction sector of Bangladesh and identified some recruitment and selection strategies for hiring staff in international project.

6.4 Practical Implications

This study is helpful for the international companies of China, who want to recruit and select employees in their international projects. The companies can follow this recruitment process as well as this recruitment and selection medium to hire manager for project manager and human resource manager in Bangladesh. The study is also important for other local and national companies for hiring project manager.

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Appendix

Dear Respondents,

As a part of my master degree in Project Management in Shandong University, I am conducting this survey to gain understanding of recruitment and selection strategies for international projects. Kindly complete this questionnaire as objectively as possible. The information given out is solely for academic purpose and would be treated as confidential.

It would take around 5 minutes. Thank you for your time and cooperation.

Section A: Personal Data

1. Company Name:

2. Email:

3. Gender

a) Male

b) Female

4. How long have you been working at your current company?

a) Less than 1 year

b) 1 – 6 years

c) 7 – 12 years

d) 13 – 18 years

e) 19 years and above

5. Which of the qualifications below do you possess?

a) Secondary

b) Undergraduate

c) Graduate

d) HND

Section B:

1. Which managers are best placed to conduct interviews? (You can select more multiple)

1. HR Manager
2. Project Manager
3. Others

2. Your company has any formal policy for the recruitment and selection of project team members for international projects.

- 1) Strongly Disagree
- 2) Disagree
- 3) Neutral
- 4) Agree
- 5) Strongly Agree

3. The job vacancies made open to the public.

- 1) Strongly Disagree
- 2) Disagree
- 3) Neutral
- 4) Agree
- 5) Strongly Agree

4. Your company provide equal opportunities for all would-be (potential) project team members when it comes to recruitment and selection.

- 1) Strongly Disagree
- 2) Disagree

3) Neutral

4) Agree

5) Strongly Agree

5. Both local and international team members are given equal consideration during the recruitment process.

1) Strongly Disagree

2) Disagree

3) Neutral

4) Agree

5) Strongly Agree

6. When vacancies occur, are existing project team members considered?

1) Strongly Disagree

2) Disagree

3) Neutral

4) Agree

5) Strongly Agree

7. Your company's human resources policies allow employees to secure promotions when they are assigned to projects.

1) Strongly Disagree

2) Disagree

3) Neutral

4) Agree

5) Strongly Agree

8. If a project is over, are the employees retained?

1. Yes

2. No

9. At the end of the project, will these permanent employees go back to the positions they held before they were given the project.

1. Yes

2. No

10. Your company outlines job analysis (i.e. duties, responsibilities, skills etc. required for particular projects) before advertising vacancies for projects.

1) Strongly Disagree

2) Disagree

3) Neutral

4) Agree

5) Strongly Agree

11. What are some skills your company looks for during project team recruitment? (You can select more multiple)

1) Problem-solving ability

2) Availability

3) Technological expertise

4) Credibility

5) Local and Political connections

6) Ambition, initiative, and energy

7) Others

12. Which of these factor(s) for recruitment and selection of project team members are regarded as most important? (You can select more multiple)

a) Academic qualifications

b) Work experience

c) Interview

d) Test

13. Which of these methods is applicable for project team members' recruitment in your Company?

1) Advertisement

2) Employee referrals

3) Employment agencies

14. Your company relies on any agent(s) and recruitment agencies for the recruitment and selection of employees in the company.

1) Strongly Disagree

2) Disagree

3) Neutral

4) Agree

5) Strongly Agree

15. At your company all the recruitment activities be managed centrally, or will each project team manage its own hiring?

.....
.16. What are some of the challenges that your company associated with while recruitment and selection practices of project team members for international projects?

.....
17. What factors will improve recruitment and selection practices at your Company for any specific project?

.....
18. What measures will have to be taken in order to keep talents who are in high demand on the market inside the company?

.....

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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